

1 **Prepulse inhibition of the blink reflex in functional** 2 **neurological disorder and fibromyalgia**

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5 **Abstract**

6 Prepulse inhibition reflects subcortical sensory integration, where a low-intensity peripheral
7 stimulus (prepulse) reduces the amplitude of a reflex response to a subsequent high-intensity
8 stimulus. As a measure of pre-attentive sensory gating, prepulse inhibition has been found to be
9 altered in small cohorts of patients with functional disorders, including functional motor disorder
10 and fibromyalgia, suggesting a shared deficit in sensory information processing. However, prior
11 studies have not demonstrated consistent associations between prepulse inhibition abnormalities
12 and clinical measures.

13 We hypothesized that widespread pain and somatic symptoms in somatic symptom disorders may
14 result from a general deficit in the interpretation of bodily signals, potentially linked to
15 abnormalities in sensory filtering as measured by prepulse inhibition.

16 In this study, we examined 140 participants across four age- and sex-matched groups: 35 patients
17 clinically categorized with functional motor disorder without fibromyalgia, 35 with both functional
18 motor disorder and fibromyalgia, 35 with fibromyalgia only, and 35 healthy controls. A weak
19 electrical stimulus to the index finger served as the prepulse, delivered 100 ms before supraorbital
20 nerve stimulation to elicit the R2 component of the blink reflex. Prepulse inhibition was calculated
21 as the percent reduction in R2 amplitude.

22 Across all groups, lower prepulse was significantly associated with higher scores on the
23 Fibromyalgia Severity Scale, consisting of Widespread Pain Index and Symptom Severity Scale.

24 In patients with functional motor disorder, no association was found between prepulse inhibition

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1 size and objectively rated motor symptom severity.

2 These findings suggest that impaired early sensory processing at subcortical level is related to
3 “fibromyalgias” in people with functional motor disorder and fibromyalgia. Abnormal prepulse
4 inhibition may serve as an objective transdiagnostic marker of fibromyalgia symptomatology or
5 fibromyalgias, including widespread pain and other non-motor symptoms in functional
6 disorders, highlighting a potential role of sensory gating deficits in the pathophysiology of
7 fibromyalgia-spectrum manifestations.

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27

1 Introduction

2 Integration of competing sensory inputs is crucial: it helps prevent sensory overload and allows
3 more effective processing of relevant information.¹ Prepulse Inhibition (PPI) is a robust
4 neurophysiological phenomenon in which a sensory stimulus (the prepulse) too weak to trigger a
5 reflex on its own, reduces the intensity of a reflex response to a stronger stimulus presented 30 to
6 500 milliseconds later (**Fig. 1**). PPI is widely accepted as a key measure of sensorimotor gating, a
7 physiological mechanism that regulates sensory input by integration of competing stimuli.² The
8 top-down regulation of PPI appears to have a critical relationship with the cortico-striatal-pallidal-
9 thalamic network (or more broadly forebrain) input to brainstem.²

10 PPI has been found consistently reduced in people with schizophrenia, obsessive-compulsive
11 disorder, anxiety disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder, Huntington's disease, and Tourette
12 syndrome.³ Interestingly, PPI has also been found abnormal in two major subtypes of functional
13 neurological disorders (FNDs): functional seizures and functional motor disorders (FMD)^{4,5} as well
14 as in somatic symptom disorders with pain such as fibromyalgia,⁶ interstitial cystitis⁷ and irritable
15 bowel syndrome.⁸ While the primary symptoms of FND relate to motor disorders, seizures and
16 sensory loss, pain is also commonly present in people with FND and is typically rated by patients
17 as a major contributor to disability and impaired quality of life.⁹ Chronic pain conditions including
18 fibromyalgia, which is characterized by widespread pain seem to be more frequent in people with
19 FND.¹⁰ FND and fibromyalgia share common non-motor symptoms, including fatigue, cognitive
20 issues, sleep disturbances, and headaches.¹¹⁻¹³ FND and other somatic symptom disorders are
21 associated with alterations in the functioning of brain networks and are now believed to share
22 underlying pathophysiological mechanisms. Recent theoretical models based on predictive coding
23 accounts of brain function suggest functional symptoms arise from the development of abnormal
24 predictions about motor and sensory states including pain, driven by an abnormal allocation of
25 attention.¹⁴ People with FMD also exhibit poor sensory discrimination, compatible with
26 underweighting of incoming sensory evidence, especially if the inputs are noisy.^{15,16}

27 Deficient PPI found in people with different functional symptoms/syndromes might suggest that
28 an impairment in ability to integrate sensory inputs could be a common neural mechanism
29 operating at subcortical level under control of top-down forebrain influences. A lack of sufficient
30 filtering or integration could result in increased sensory noise, which in turn could more easily be

1 over-ridden by prior expectations.⁵
2 In studies examining PPI in people with functional symptoms (FND and somatic symptom
3 disorders) only a limited number have assessed the relationship between PPI deficits and clinical
4 measures.^{4,5} Notably, these studies have not found significant correlations between PPI
5 abnormalities and symptom severity. For instance, research on patients with FMD reported no
6 significant association between motor and non-motor symptom measures (including pain intensity)
7 and PPI size.

8 Recent advances in fibromyalgia research have led to revision of diagnostic criteria and to
9 development of a diagnostic self-reported measures of pain widespreadness and number and
10 severity of other non-motor symptoms such as fatigue, poor sleep, mood and cognitive
11 problems.^{12,17} Fibromyalgia is increasingly viewed not as a discrete disease but as a spectrum of
12 “fibromyalgianess”, defined by pain widespreadness and symptom severity scores, and extending
13 to individuals with symptoms who do not meet full diagnostic criteria across clinical and non-
14 clinical populations.¹⁸ We hypothesized that widespread pain and perceived symptom burdens
15 could result from a general deficit in misinterpretation of bodily signals in people diagnosed with
16 fibromyalgia and FND linked to insufficient filtering of sensory information as measured by PPI.

17 The aim of this study was to perform a comprehensive investigation of PPI in fibromyalgia and
18 FND, with a particular focus on the relationship between PPI abnormalities and symptom severity
19 rather than on differences between groups with different categorical diagnoses. To achieve this, we
20 studied the association of PPI magnitude and fibromyalgia-related symptom severity on a
21 continuum of fibromyalgianess in three groups of patients with clinically diagnosed FMD and/or
22 fibromyalgia together with age and sex-matched healthy individuals. In addition, association
23 between PPI size and objectively rated motor symptom severity was studied in patients with FMD,
24 both with and without comorbid fibromyalgia.

25

26 **Materials and methods**

27 One hundred and forty subjects were recruited to the study between January 2022 and March 2024.
28 Exclusion criteria for both the control and patient groups included being under 18 years old,
29 language difficulties, severe learning disabilities or cognitive impairment, significant illnesses

1 associated with non-motor symptoms, substance dependence, psychosis, or a history of organic
2 neurological brain disorders and medication known to affect PPI, such as dopamine receptor
3 antagonists. All participants gave their written consent to take part in the study. The project was
4 approved by the Ethics Committee of the General Teaching Hospital in Prague, approval number:
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6 Individuals with fibromyalgia were recruited directly by a rheumatologist (co-authors JZ, LH, LŠ)
7 from Institute of Rheumatology in Prague ($n = 6$) or through an online support group for patients
8 with fibromyalgia ($n = 29$). All individuals recruited online had rheumatological assessment and
9 provided a medical report. The diagnosis of fibromyalgia in all fibromyalgia patients was also
10 validated by a fibromyalgia diagnostic questionnaire.¹⁷

11 FMD patients were recruited at the specialized outpatient service for FMD at the Neurology
12 Department, 1st Faculty of Medicine and General University Hospital in Prague to match
13 fibromyalgia patients by age and sex. Two groups of FMD patients were recruited with and without
14 comorbid fibromyalgia, which was diagnosed using the current criteria based on fibromyalgia
15 diagnostic questionnaire.¹⁷

16 Control subjects matching the FMD and fibromyalgia patients for age and sex were identified in a
17 directory of healthy individuals willing to participate in clinical studies operated at the Neurology
18 Department. They underwent a thorough screening process, including a complete medical history
19 and a full neurological examination, ensuring that none had sensorimotor symptoms or objective
20 signs of neurological disorders. All control subjects received financial compensation of \$25.

21 All subjects underwent a full neurological assessment including a detailed clinical interview and
22 examination by a neurologist with expertise in FMD (co-authors TS, LN), focusing on positive
23 signs of functional weakness or abnormal movements that were inconsistent and incongruent with
24 known movement disorders. FMD diagnosis was established using the Gupta and Lang criteria for
25 a clinically definite FMD.¹⁹ In each individual diagnosed with FMD, we evaluated and categorized
26 motor symptoms phenomenologically as functional weakness, tremor, dystonia/spasm, myoclonus,
27 gait abnormalities, or speech difficulties. We noted the primary motor symptom type along with
28 any additional motor symptoms exhibited.

29 Assessment of fibromyalgia was performed using the 2016 Fibromyalgia Survey Questionnaire,
30 which allowed to diagnose fibromyalgia based on the 2016 revised American College of

1 Rheumatology diagnostic criteria.¹⁷ To meet the criteria for fibromyalgia diagnosis, the individual
2 must have a Widespread Pain Index (WPI) of 7 or higher and a Symptom Severity Scale (SSS)
3 score of 5 or higher. Alternatively, if the WPI is between 4 and 6, the SSS score must be 9 or higher.
4 The individual must also have generalized pain, defined as pain in at least four of five regions, and
5 symptoms must have been generally present for at least three months. The Symptom Severity Scale
6 includes the following symptoms: fatigue, waking unrefreshed, cognitive symptoms, headaches,
7 pain or cramps in the lower abdomen, and depression.¹⁷ The WPI and SSS scores can also be
8 combined to provide a Fibromyalgia Severity Score (FSS), which is used as a continuous measure
9 of fibromyalginess ranging between 0 and 31.

10 Individuals with fibromyalgia, FMD and fibromyalgia, FMD alone and HC were age and sex
11 matched.

12 All participants included in the study completed questionnaires for depression, anxiety, and
13 subjective cognitive complaints.

14 The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II) was used to measure depressive symptoms. It consists of
15 21 items with total score range of 0 to 63.²⁰

16 We assessed anxiety levels using the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory trait scale specifically the STAI
17 X-2: a 20-item measure of trait anxiety with a possible score range of 20 to 80.²¹

18 Motor disorder severity was assessed using the Simplified FMD Rating Scale (S-FMDRS).
19 Abnormal movements were recorded across seven body regions and rated based on the severity
20 and duration of symptoms, with a maximum possible score of 54.²²

21 Furthermore, all subjects' pharmacological history (SSRI, SNRI, SARI, NaSA, TCA,
22 anticonvulsants, DA, BDZ, opioids, NSA, medical cannabis) was recorded in detail (See
23 **Supplementary Table S1**). None of the subjects used medication known to affect PPI, such as
24 dopamine receptor antagonists.²³⁻²⁵

25 A structured interview was conducted to identify medical comorbidities, family history, current
26 medications (including hormonal contraceptives), drug use, smoking habits, caffeine
27 consumption, and handedness. Participants were asked to refrain from caffeine and smoking for
28 3–4 hours prior to PPI testing to minimize known acute effects of these substances on
29 sensorimotor gating and reduce interindividual variability.^{6,26-28}

1 **Neurophysiological examination**

2 The neurophysiological examination was conducted under standard conditions in a moderately lit
3 and quiet room. The subject was seated comfortably, ensuring that the electromyographic device
4 was not within their line of sight to prevent anticipation of the stimuli delivery. The subject was
5 informed in advance about the different types of stimuli. The recording was performed using a
6 routinely employed electrodiagnostic device (Synergy, CareFusion, London, United Kingdom).
7 The band-pass filters were set to frequencies ranging from 30 Hz to 30,000 Hz, with a sampling
8 frequency of 2,000 Hz.

9 **Paradigm**

10 The examination involved electromyographic recording of muscle activity in the orbicularis oculi
11 using 10 mm gold surface electrodes with conductive gel. The active electrode was placed along
12 the midline under the eye, dividing the muscle into two symmetrical parts, while the reference
13 electrode was positioned 2 cm laterally toward the outer corner of each eye. To elicit the blink
14 reflex, a 0.5 ms rectangular pulse of constant current was delivered to the right supraorbital nerve.
15 The cathode was placed over the supraorbital incisura, and the anode was positioned 3 cm laterally
16 along the nerve's path over the eyebrow.

17 The stimulation intensity applied was 10 times the individual's sensory threshold, which is defined
18 as the smallest stimulus intensity perceived by the subject in at least 4 out of 8 applications. A
19 prepulse stimulus, consisting of a 0.2 ms rectangular pulse of constant current, was applied 100 ms
20 before the supraorbital nerve stimulation, using ring electrodes attached to the right index finger
21 over the proximal and medial phalanges. A 100 ms interval between the prepulse and the startle
22 stimulus was used to ensure reliable inhibition of the blink reflex and consistency with previous
23 PPI studies of the blink reflex in FMD and fibromyalgia.^{5,6,29} The prepulse stimulation intensity
24 was set at twice the subject's sensory threshold. Each subject underwent 9 stimulations of the
25 supraorbital nerve alone (baseline blink reflex) and 9 stimulations with a prepulse preceding the
26 supraorbital nerve stimulation (blink reflex with prepulse), with approximately 8-10 second pauses
27 between individual stimulations.

28 During the baseline trials and prepulse trial, the morphology of blink reflex (R1, R2, and R3
29 components) was carefully assessed, and only trials from individuals with the R1 component

1 demonstrating no change or increase in the prepulse trials were included in the study. The
2 examination also involved assessing the subject's perceived discomfort or pain using the Numerical
3 Rating Scale for Pain (NRS), where 0 indicates no discomfort and 10 represents unbearable pain.

4 **Analysis**

5 Electromyographic recordings were rectified and analysed offline. Each subject underwent 18
6 stimulations (9 for the blink reflex and 9 for the blink reflex with prepulse). The early R1 and late
7 R2 components were identified in each ipsilateral EMG recording of the blink reflex, with the R2
8 component also recorded contralaterally (R2c). The magnitude of the R2 and R2c blink reflexes
9 was measured as the area under the curve (ms/mV) and averaged. In some recordings, an R3
10 component, a late polyphasic part of the blink reflex, was also observed but was not included in
11 the analysis.

12 To evaluate PPI, we calculated the average blink reflex magnitude (R2 and R2c areas) for each
13 trial. For each individual, we averaged the values from nine trials per condition (baseline and
14 prepulse).

15 To normalize data among subjects, we expressed the change in blink reflex magnitude during
16 prepulse trials relative to baseline trials as a percentage of the baseline trials ($\%PPI = \text{mean blink}$
17 $\text{reflex magnitude in prepulse trials} / \text{mean blink reflex magnitude in baseline trials} \times 100$). The
18 primary outcome, PPI size, was calculated as the difference in blink reflex magnitude between the
19 prepulse ($\%PPI$) and baseline trials (100 %), i.e. $PPI \text{ size} = 100\% - \%PPI$. The PPI size value
20 represents the primary outcome and reflects the degree of prepulse inhibition in a given subject.
21 Blink reflex recordings from all participants were of sufficient quality to allow for further analysis.

22 **Statistics**

23 Multiple linear regression model of FSS as measure of fibromyalgiansess was fitted with PPI as the
24 predictor, adjusting for age and sex to account for potential confounding effects. Additionally, we
25 also fitted similar models of WPI and SSS. Because depression and anxiety are strongly associated
26 with chronic pain³⁰ and may act as mediators of the relationship between PPI size and fibromyalgia
27 symptoms, we did not include them as covariates in these models. We also examined whether PPI
28 size was associated with motor symptom severity in a subset of patients with FMD, including those

1 with comorbid fibromyalgia ($n = 70$), to assess whether reduced PPI size is specific to pain
2 symptoms within FMD or also relates to motor symptom severity.

3 Additionally, group differences in demographic and clinical characteristics (age, illness duration,
4 FSS, WPI, SSS, S-FMDRS, BDI-II, and STAI-X2) were assessed using analysis of variance with
5 Tukey post hoc tests. Pearson's correlation was used to assess the relationship between PPI size
6 and other symptom measures, including the BDI-II, STAI-X2, and S-FMDRS. Analyses were
7 performed in R (Version 4.4).³¹ P-values arising from multiple statistical testing were corrected
8 using the Holm-Bonferroni method.³²

9

10 **Ethical Compliance Statement**

11 The study was approved by the local Ethics Committee of the General University Hospital in
12 Prague (Approval Nr. 37/19) and all participants gave their written consent to take part in the study.
13 We confirm that we have read the Journal's position on issues involved in ethical publication and
14 affirm that this work is consistent with those guidelines.

15

16 **Results**

17 A total of 140 participants were included in the analysis, comprising 35 subjects per patient group
18 and 35 healthy controls. All patient cohorts and healthy controls were matched for key
19 demographics with no differences in age or sex among the groups. Demographic data and clinical
20 scores are summarized in **Supplementary Table S2**. Post hoc tests showed that the illness duration
21 was significantly longer in fibromyalgia patients as compared to FMD with fibromyalgia ($P = 0.01$)
22 and FMD patients ($P < 0.001$), but the illness duration between FMD and FMD with fibromyalgia
23 did not differ ($P = 0.61$). Healthy controls reported significantly lower FSS, WPI, SSS, BDI-II, and
24 STAI-X2 scores compared to all patient cohorts ($P < 0.001$). Fibromyalgia only and FMD with
25 fibromyalgia patients had significantly higher FSS, WPI, SSS scores ($P < 0.001$), BDI-II and STAI-
26 X2 scores ($P < 0.01$) compared to FMD group. S-FMDRS was significantly higher in FMD with
27 fibromyalgia patients compared to FMD only patients ($P < 0.001$). There were no significant
28 differences in the clinical scales between fibromyalgia only and FMD with fibromyalgia patients.

1
2 In the full sample of all patients and healthy controls, three multiple linear regression models were
3 conducted to examine whether fibromyalgia-related symptom severity, as measured by the FSS,
4 WPI, and SSS is predicted by PPI size, age, and sex. The regression model for FSS explained
5 22.5% of the variance, $F(3, 136) = 14.43, P < 0.001$. (**Fig. 2.**) The models for WPI and SSS
6 explained 19.6% and 19.9% of the variance, respectively [WPI: $F(3, 136) = 12.26, P < 0.001$;
7 SSS:(3, 136) = 12.52, $P < 0.001$].

8
9 Across all three models, PPI size was a significant negative predictor after adjusting for sex and
10 age, indicating that lower PPI was associated with greater fibromyalgia-related symptom severity.
11 Full regression coefficients are presented in **Table 1**.

12
13 A multiple linear regression was conducted to examine whether PPI size, age, and sex predicted
14 motor symptom severity, as measured by the S-FMDRS, in a subset of patients with FMD ($n = 70$).
15 The model did not explain the S-FMDRS scores in a significant way, $F(3, 66) = 1.50, P = 0.22$,
16 with an adjusted R^2 of 0.02. PPI size was not a significant predictor [$t(66) = -0.33, P = 0.75$], nor
17 were age [$t(66) = 1.82, P = 0.066$] or sex [$t(66) = -0.80, P = 0.42$]. These findings suggest that PPI
18 size is not associated with motor symptom severity in this patient subgroup.

19
20 To further examine the specificity of the relationship between PPI size and fibromyalgia symptoms,
21 we conducted a multiple regression analysis predicting FSS from PPI size, adjusting for the effects
22 of S-FMDRS scores, age, and sex. The model accounted for 14.7% of the variance in fibromyalgia
23 symptom severity, $F(4, 65) = 3.97, P = 0.006$. PPI size remained a significant negative predictor
24 of fibromyalgia symptoms [$-0.10, t(65) = -2.58, P = 0.019$], even after adjusting for motor symptom
25 severity. S-FMDRS was also a significant predictor [$0.25, t(65) = 2.55, P = 0.016$], while age and
26 sex were not associated with fibromyalgia severity. These results suggest that reduced PPI size is
27 specifically associated with pain-related symptoms in FMD, independent of motor symptom
28 burden.

29

1 Examples of blink reflex responses without and with prepulse stimulation in a patient and a healthy
2 control subject are shown in **Fig. 3**.

3

4 **Additional analyses**

5 Correlation analysis (**Supplementary Fig. S1**) revealed a negative association between PPI size
6 and fibromyalgia-related measures (FSS, WPI, SSS) and affective symptoms (BDI-II, STAI-X2),
7 but no correlation with motor symptom severity (S-FMDRS). To further support the view of
8 fibromyalginess as a continuum, the ANOVA model showed that between-group differences in
9 PPI size (**Supplementary Fig. S2A**) disappeared after adjustment for fibromyalgia severity (FSS)
10 (**Supplementary Fig. S2B**), indicating that these differences were artefacts of the strong negative
11 correlation with fibromyalgia-related scales and artificial diagnostic cut-offs.

12

13 **Discussion**

14 In this study, we analysed PPI size as a measure of subcortical early processing and integration of
15 sensory information³³ across individuals with two conditions with partially overlapping symptoms,
16 FMD and fibromyalgia. Reduced PPI size was associated with higher scores of fibromyalginess
17 across all participants. In FMD, comorbid fibromyalgia was associated with more severe motor
18 symptoms; however, clinician-rated motor symptom severity was not predicted by PPI size. These
19 findings suggest that PPI size is a relevant physiological marker of fibromyalginess, rather than
20 motor symptom severity.

21 Extensive research has identified the neuroanatomical and neurochemical substrates of PPI,
22 particularly within the forebrain and pontine tegmentum, with the ventral striatum playing a central
23 role in this regulatory network.³³⁻³⁷ PPI reflects early, pre-attentive filtering of sensory information,
24 protecting ongoing stimulus processing from disruption.³⁸ PPI size is influenced by stimulus
25 salience and reflects automatic selection processes that occur before conscious awareness.^{29,39-42}
26 Without intact PPI, low-salience stimuli may fail to be appropriately integrated with or filtered
27 against competing high-salience inputs, resulting in decreased sensory fidelity and a noisier
28 perceptual environment for subsequent processing. Disruptions in PPI have been observed in a

1 range of (but not all) neuropsychiatric disorders,^{33,43} including both motor and seizure subtypes of
2 FND,^{4,5} as well as some somatic symptom disorders with prominent pain.⁶⁻⁸ Abnormal PPI has
3 been associated with different pathophysiological mechanisms reflecting diverse underlying
4 mechanisms, including genetic vulnerability and neural circuit dysfunction (**Fig. 4**).^{33,44} As such,
5 PPI is increasingly recognized as a transdiagnostic marker of impaired sensorimotor gating in
6 psychopathology.

7 Here, we extended previous findings of PPI deficits from small sample studies comparing healthy
8 controls with a single clinical group with FMD or fibromyalgia.^{6,9} In contrast to the previous
9 fibromyalgia study ($n = 10$),⁶ we used current diagnostic criteria for fibromyalgia which are based
10 on self-reported widespread pain and the severity of other somatic and psychological symptoms
11 (i.e. fibromyalginess) using predefined cut-offs.¹⁷ However, varying degree of fibromyalginess
12 exists in healthy subjects and various clinical populations. It has been pointed out that reported
13 neurobiological and imaging abnormalities in fibromyalgia may largely reflect sampling bias from
14 dichotomizing patients and selecting only extremes of symptom severity distribution.¹⁸ In line with
15 these observations, the between-group differences in PPI size found in this study disappeared after
16 adjustment for FSS, indicating that the apparent effects were an artefact of the correlation between
17 PPI and fibromyalgia severity and of categorical classification based on diagnostic cut-offs.

18 In this study, using fibromyalginess as the outcome measure allowed us to move beyond
19 categorical diagnoses with arbitrary cut-off values and instead examine illness features across four
20 matched groups, including individuals with overlapping conditions and healthy controls. The
21 clinical correlates of PPI deficits across clinical populations remain poorly understood. For the first
22 time, we report an association between PPI size and fibromyalginess across all groups of subjects,
23 including healthy controls. This finding aligns with prior literature on reduced PPI in different
24 chronic pain conditions such as fibromyalgia, interstitial cystitis and irritable bowel syndrome,⁶⁻⁸
25 but also findings in migraine patients showing that PPI reduction is more likely in those with
26 allodynia.⁴⁵ In a separate analysis of patients with FMD (with and without fibromyalgia), we found
27 that PPI size was associated with fibromyalginess, but not with clinician-rated motor symptom
28 severity. These findings support the interpretation that reduced PPI is associated with perceived
29 non-motor symptom severity in FND, i.e. subjective experience of fibromyalginess. Indeed, self-
30 reported symptom severity measures are strongly intercorrelated in FMD in this and other studies,
31 likely reflecting a perceptual impairment across multiple symptom domains.⁹ Future research

1 should explore how PPI interacts with other biological, psychological, and social factors across
2 diagnostic boundaries to better understand symptom development and maintenance.

3 A key principle of the current neurobiological model based on predictive coding account is that the
4 same neural/computational mechanism can account for all functional symptoms including pain,
5 regardless of specific phenotype.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ This model highlights the role of abnormal (symptom
6 specific), overly precise expectations that overwhelm incoming sensory data which would indicate
7 the absence of the specific symptom. However, the results from this study suggest that different
8 symptoms (motor vs. fibromyalgias) coexisting within one individual do not share the same
9 neurophysiological signature. PPI seems to be a specific transdiagnostic biomarker of
10 fibromyalgias. We can hypothesise that while PPI size is linked to symptom
11 perception/experience, the motor symptoms could be more directly associated with motor outputs,
12 involving distinct underlying circuits and functional anatomy. Abnormal top-down regulatory
13 mechanisms that mediate PPI, involving projections from forebrain structures to the pontine reflex
14 circuitry, are likely the primary network responsible for impaired PPI in fibromyalgia and in FMD
15 in which it seems to be associated with non-motor symptoms severity including pain.

16 In patients with FND and fibromyalgia, functional imaging studies have shown dysfunction in the
17 salience network, including the ventral striatum and amygdala, and in the ventral attention
18 network.^{14,49-57} These networks are crucial for detecting salient stimuli and reorienting focus, as
19 well as integrating contextual information through bottom-up and top-down interactions and
20 attentional shifts.^{40,58,59} Abnormal processing of physiologically salient stimuli and disrupted
21 attentional shifts in FND could be related to PPI impairment in this disorder. There is evidence in
22 FMD of abnormalities in sensory processing, which would be consistent with an abnormality in
23 sensory integration, resulting in noisy early stages of sensory processing.²⁹ This was the conclusion
24 of previous work showing abnormalities in temporal discrimination in people with motor subtype
25 of FND, where data analysis using drift diffusion modelling suggested abnormalities in evidence
26 accumulation.^{15,55} There is also evidence for impaired processing of interoceptive information in
27 both FND and fibromyalgia.^{56,57} This raises the possibility that impaired PPI could reflect both a
28 trait abnormality that makes people more vulnerable to developing FND, fibromyalgia, or other
29 functional disorders, and a marker of the current state of downregulation of sensory input in
30 established illness.

1 The association between PPI size and fibromyalginess across all groups of subjects is an important
2 finding, as PPI is considered to be a stable neurophysiological marker in healthy individuals.^{60,61}
3 In schizophrenia, a higher heritability of reduced PPI was found in families with a strong genetic
4 predisposition, suggesting that PPI deficits may indicate genetic vulnerability.⁶² This vulnerability
5 could potentially be associated with other neuropsychiatric disorders including FND, and their
6 common comorbidities affecting PPI such as obsessive compulsive disorder, generalised anxiety
7 disorder and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD).⁶³ For example, a longitudinal study of 1226 US
8 Marines and Navy Corpsmen found that individuals in the top 25% of PPI had over a 50% reduced
9 likelihood of developing PTSD after deployment (odds ratio = 0.32), suggesting strong
10 sensorimotor gating may protect against PTSD.⁶³ Abnormal PPI could also indicate a link between
11 genetic risk variants and more direct lower-level biological processes contributing to observable
12 symptoms. This would be consistent both with known risk factors for FND and fibromyalgia, such
13 as traumatic experiences, depression, anxiety, neurodiversity and joint hypermobility which are all
14 characterised by abnormalities in interoceptive and more general sensory processing and also
15 impaired PPI in their own right.^{64,65} There is evidence suggesting that noisy information is more
16 prone to be overridden by top-down expectations, such as the less precise visceral input mediated
17 by the autonomous nervous system, i.e. interoceptive information.⁶⁶ We can speculate that if
18 abnormal expectations are formed in a brain that is unable to efficiently filter the incoming sensory
19 signals, the expectations are more likely to overwhelm such noisy inputs and result in development
20 and maintenance of functional symptoms.¹² Our findings thereby challenge the central sensitization
21 hypothesis still prevalent in fibromyalgia literature¹² which assumes heightened sensitivity to
22 peripheral input; however, there is a lack of neurophysiological correlates to behavioral readouts
23 of chronic pain in studies on central sensitization in humans.⁶⁷ Instead, our results imply that the
24 system is *less* sensitive to peripheral input, leaving perception disproportionately shaped by top-
25 down predictions.

26 In this study, we have linked an objective neurophysiological marker to subjectively reported
27 fibromyalginess, which has been found to be a useful prognostic factor for outcomes for several
28 types of interventions, including pain following hip surgery or persistent pelvic pain after
29 hysterectomy.^{68,69} Higher scores have been associated with worse outcomes, even in individuals
30 who do not meet the full diagnostic criteria for fibromyalgia.⁷⁰ So far, objective markers of
31 widespread pain are limited/lacking. Further studies should address the utility of PPI size as an

1 objective measure of widespread pain and it's associated with clinical outcomes for people
2 undergoing surgical procedures for chronic pain.⁷¹ Further studies using multimodal approaches
3 are needed to identify specific neurophysiological profiles (including other neurophysiological
4 measures such as assessment of cortical inhibitory mechanisms previously reported to be abnormal
5 in FMD^{72,73} or combinations of neurophysiological and laboratory and neuroimaging pain markers.
6 Moreover, current and previous studies have found normal PPI in some individuals with these
7 disorders and reduced levels in some healthy individuals. This could reflect the limitations of
8 diagnostic classifications, as clinical criteria, though established through expert consensus, are
9 somewhat arbitrary. Research indicates that individuals who meet the diagnostic criteria for a
10 disorder and those who narrowly miss the cutoff often share significant similarities, differing
11 mainly in the number and severity of symptoms. Therefore, examining the impact of comorbidities,
12 cognitive measures, and therapeutic interventions, along with deep phenotyping and identifying
13 FND and fibromyalgia subtypes, could uncover neurophysiological mechanisms and advance
14 neurotherapeutic development addressing core dysfunctions rather than disorder-specific
15 symptoms. Other factors, such as sleep disturbance, which is known to affect PPI and is prevalent
16 in both fibromyalgia and FMD,⁷⁴⁻⁷⁷ was not specifically assessed in this study; future research
17 should examine its potential contribution to altered sensorimotor gating in these populations. PPI
18 shows promise as a transdiagnostic endophenotype for genomic studies and a biomarker for a
19 healthy brain circuitry, which may predict sensitivity to psychotherapeutics.^{25,33} Future research
20 could explore whether the associations found in this study exist in other populations, such as
21 schizophrenia. This would also help clarify whether PPI can serve as a transdiagnostic marker
22 measuring somatosensory integration or early attentional processing mechanisms related to
23 symptom perception in different populations rather than being a generalized index of disease
24 presence.

25 A single marker is unlikely to sufficiently explain such complex and overlapping disorders, so
26 these findings highlight the need for future research on combined markers. Previous pain research
27 has identified other promising markers.⁷⁸ For example, laser evoked potentials have shown
28 correlation of amplitude with nociceptive stimulation intensity suggestive of top down processing
29 impairment; EEG studies have identified correlations between pain and the power at different EEG
30 frequency bands; other potential correlates of chronic pain include laboratory markers such as beta
31 endorphine, CGRP, VIP, SP, endocannabinoids (AEA and 2-AG) and serum derived soluble

1 intercellular adhesion molecule1 (sICAM-1), and a specific neuroimaging pattern correlating with
2 fibromyalgians has been identified.⁷⁸ It may be, like PPI, that such markers are not specific to
3 fibromyalgia or even to the presence of widespread pain but might also occur in people with FND
4 without fibromyalgia.

5 In conclusion, we found a deficit of PPI that suggests abnormal early processing of somatosensory
6 inputs in FND and fibromyalgia. A lower PPI size was associated with more fibromyalgians i.e.
7 pain widespreadness and higher levels of non-motor symptoms in people with fibromyalgia and
8 FMD. PPI thus could represent a valuable objective marker of generalised chronic pain and
9 associated non-motor symptoms in this clinical population.

10

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14

15 **Data availability**

16 The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding
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18

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25

1 **Competing interests**

2 The authors report no competing interests.

3

4 **Supplementary material**

5 Supplementary material is available at *Brain* online.

6

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21

22 **Figure legends**

23 **Figure 1 Prepulse Inhibition scheme.** Prepulse inhibition is a neurophysiological phenomenon in
24 which a reflexive response (e.g. the startle response or the blink reflex) to a strong stimulus (pulse)
25 is significantly reduced when preceded by a weaker stimulus (prepulse) within 30 to 500
26 milliseconds. The prepulse alone is too weak to elicit a reflex but effectively modulates the
27 subsequent response. Prepulse inhibition serves as a key measure of sensorimotor gating, a

1 fundamental mechanism that regulates sensory input by filtering out irrelevant or disruptive
2 signals.³³ (Created in BioRender)

3
4 **Figure 2 The relation between fibromyalgiansess and prepulse inhibition.** On average, a
5 decrease of prepulse inhibition (PPI size) by 10%, was linked to an increase of fibromyalgiansess
6 (FSS) by 2 in a model of FSS explained in terms of PPI size, age, and sex (gray line). FSS values
7 were slightly jittered to ease visual perception of overlapping values. C = Healthy controls; F =
8 Fibromyalgia; M = Functional Motor Disorder; O = Functional Motor Disorder and Fibromyalgia;
9 FSS = Fibromyalgia Severity Scale; PPI size = Prepulse Inhibition size (i.e. the difference between
10 the mean blink reflex magnitude in the baseline trials and the trials with the prepulse expressed in
11 %).

12
13 **Figure 3 Blink reflex recordings in a patient with functional motor disorder and a healthy**
14 **control.** A representative example of the blink reflex recordings elicited by the electrical
15 supraorbital nerve stimulation (pulse) without (upper two traces) and with prepulse stimulation
16 (lower two traces) in an FMD patient (left) and a control subject (right). Blue arrow indicates
17 prepulse stimulus to index finger. Red arrow indicates the supraorbital nerve stimulation. Note that
18 the suppression of the R2 and R2c area under the curve was lower in the patient than in the control.
19 Created in BioRender. Nováková, L. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/oya9ami>.

20
21 **Figure 4 Neural circuitry and contributing factors influencing prepulse inhibition.** Top-down
22 regulatory mechanisms that mediate prepulse inhibition involve projections from forebrain
23 structures. This cortico-striato-pallido-pontine circuitry involving the prefrontal cortex (PFC), the
24 nucleus accumbens (NAc), the ventral pallidum (VP), the amygdala (AMY), the hippocampus
25 (HIPP), and the ventral tegmental area (VTA) projects via the tegmental pedunculopontine nucleus
26 (TgPPN) to the pontine blink reflex/startle response circuitry involving pontomedullary reticular
27 formation.³⁸ The regulatory control of prepulse inhibition mediated by the forebrain is influenced
28 by various physiological and pathophysiological factors (see box), which affect attention re-
29 orienting and stimulus-related salience attribution processes, both of which have been implicated
30 in functional neurological disorder.³³ Created in BioRender. Nováková, L. (2025)

1 <https://BioRender.com/v55wx1a>.

2

3 **Table 1 Regression coefficients for predictors of fibromyalgia-related scales**

Predictor	Outcome		
	FSS (SE)	WPI (SE)	SSS (SE)
Intercept	30.26 (4.74)***	18.39 (3.17)***	11.87 (1.96)***
PPI size	-0.21 (0.03)***	-0.13 (0.02)***	-0.08 (0.01)***
Age	-0.11 (0.08)	-0.08 (0.05)	-0.03 (0.03)
Sex	-3.68 (2.31)	-2.49 (1.54)	-1.19 (0.95)

4 Regression coefficients are reported. FSS = Fibromyalgia Severity Scale; WPI = Widespread Pain Index; SSS = Symptom Severity Scale; SE =
 5 standard error.
 6 *** $p < .001$.

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10

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Figure 1

90x88 mm (x DPI)

8

9

10

11

Figure 2
187x133 mm (x DPI)

1
2
3
4

1
2
3
4
Figure 3
246x259 mm (x DPI)

1
2
3

Figure 4
151x128 mm (x DPI)

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